

DISTRIBUTION OF FREE AND TOTAL ASCORBIC ACID IN THE LIVER AND MUSCLE OF BENGAL FRESH-WATER FISH.

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The ascorbic acid contents of the liver and muscle tissues of 34 kinds of Bengal fresh-water fish have been determined by the usual method and by the method of Sen-Gupta and Guha.

It has been shown by Rudra (*Biochem. J.*, 1936, **30**, 701) that of all parts of an animal generally used for edible purpose, the liver is the richest and the muscle the poorest in vitamin C, although considering all the tissues, the liver is not the organ richest in vitamin C. The concentration of the vitamin in the suprarenal cortex is greater than its concentration in the liver. But on account of the very minute size of the suprarenal in proportion to the liver, the latter is a greater source of the vitamin.

The present work was undertaken to investigate the ascorbic acid content of the liver and muscle tissues of some Bengal fresh-water fish and to find if any portion of the vitamin in these tissues is present in a combined form. It has been shown previously from this laboratory (Guha and co-workers, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 481, 496) that many plant foodstuffs contain part of the ascorbic acid in a combined state, which has been called ascorbigen. Guha and Sen-Gupta (*Nature*, 1938, **141**, 974) also indicated that with certain animal tissues, for example with guinea-pig brain, a greater reducing value is obtained on heating in an atmosphere of hydrogen sulphide and its specificity is shown by the fact that the bulk of it is oxidised by ascorbic acid oxidase. In the present work, therefore, we have investigated the liver and muscle tissues of 34 kinds of Bengal fish by the method of Sen Gupta and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 549; *Science and Culture*, 1938, **3**, 398; *Nature*, 1938, **141**, 974), which consists in determining the vitamin value after hot H₂S treatment and then finding which portion of this value disappears on treatment with ascorbic acid oxidase. We have called these the "true, total" ascorbic acid values. These values have been compared with those obtained by the usual technique of simple trichloroacetic acid treatment according to the method of Ghosh and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 30).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Estimation of " true total " Ascorbic Acid.

The material (10 g.) under investigation was cut into small pieces and minced uniformly by passing through an 'Enterprise' hasher twice. The minced product was then disintegrated in a glass mortar with washed sea-sand after which the mixture was taken in a suspension of 50 c. c. of water and sulphuretted hydrogen passed in. After 5 minutes the suspension was heated under reflux on a boiling water-bath, while sulphuretted hydrogen was being passed. Heating was continued for 15 minutes and then sulphuretted hydrogen was removed completely (as tested by lead acetate paper) by a current of carbon dioxide. The suspension was then treated with 2.5 c.c. of 20% trichloroacetic acid, the mixture centrifuged and the filtrate made up to 100 c.c. This solution was titrated against 0.5 c.c. of $M/10-2$: 6-dichlorophenol-indophenol to which 1 c.c. of glacial acetic acid had been previously added.

To estimate the reducing substances other than ascorbic acid, the same sample (10 g.) was treated with sulphuretted hydrogen as before and sulphuretted hydrogen was removed by carbon dioxide and centrifuged. After centrifuging, the volume of the filtrate was made up to 100 c.c. and 10 c.c. of the solution, thus obtained, were incubated with 10 c.c. of ascorbic acid oxidase solution of known potency (prepared from 400 g. of white gourd and dissolved in 250 c.c. of water) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour at p_H 5.6 at 40° with the addition of 2 c.c. of acetate buffer. After the incubation period, the solution was titrated against 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol as usual. The difference between the two readings (with and without oxidase action) gave the " total true " ascorbic acid (Sen-Gupta and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 549).

Free Ascorbic Acid by Simple Indophenol Titration.—The same sample of liver or muscle (10 g.), prepared in the way described before, was treated with 2.5 c.c. of 20% trichloroacetic acid, finely ground and taken up with 50 c.c. of water and centrifuged. The filtrate was made up to 100 c.c. and titrated against $M/10-2$:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol in the usual way.

The values given in Table I for each variety of fish are derived from estimations of 5-7 samples. The range of weights of the different individuals of each variety of fish is also given in the table.

D I S C U S S I O N .

From the results it is clear that among all the different varieties of fish investigated *koi* (*Anabas testudineus*) has the highest ascorbic acid content

TABLE I

Vitamin C in muscle and liver of Bengal fish.

Figures for ascorbic acid are given in mg. per 100 g. of the fresh tissue.

Ranges of body weight. (in g.)	Bengali name of the fish..	Zoological name	Vitamin C in muscle.		Vitamin C in liver	
			" Total true " vitamin.	Free vitamin.	" Total true " vitamin	Free vitamin.
923-223	Kalbasu	<i>Labeo Calbost</i>	10·6	9·1	64·8	60·2
28-41	Puti	...	15·3	13·7	40·1	37·6
111-325	Sarputi	<i>Barbus Sarana</i>	13·6	13·1	56·6	53·2
380-69	Vetki	<i>Latas Calcifer</i>	9·6	9·3	18·5	15·8
390-122	Pyrachanda	...	19·4	17·9	28·7	25·5
137-14	Tengra	...	17·6	18·8	54·2	47·6
75-22	Bacha	<i>Chptso magarua</i>	13·0	12·3	38·6	36·2
814-210	Ilisha	<i>Clupea Ilisha</i>	24·1	24·0	53·9	50·2
75-22	Bata	...	negligible	negligible	7·3	6
18012-416	Catla	<i>Catla catla</i>	9·3	7·2	39·0	35·7
58-15	Koi	<i>Anabas testudineous</i>	32·0	31·6	67·8	65·3
45-20	Pakal	...	negligible	negligible	21·0	18·3
423-128	Bhola	<i>Sclaena cottor</i>	13·7	12·4	64·3	58·2
3150-236	Air	<i>Arius arlus</i>	11·1	8·9	26·6	24·1
56-24	Fesha	...	negligible	negligible	17·6	16·1
1263-424	Sole	<i>Ophicephalus striatus</i>	9·2	7·6	36·7	32·2
516-56	Bele	<i>Glassgobius gluris</i>	3·1	2·7	8·2	7·6
3-11	Maurala	<i>Amblypharyn godonmola</i>	5·2	5·0	19·2	17·8
518-69	Kujavetki	...	10·2	9·7	32·6	28·8
36-75	Singhi	<i>Saccobranchus fossilis</i>	9·3	8·8	56·3	49·7
46-72	Lata	<i>Ophicephalus punetatus</i>	negligible	negligible	19·7	17·9
11-31	Parsey	<i>Mugilparsia.</i>	6·2	6·0	39·7	35·2
1327-316	Bhangar	...	12·0	11·6	56·9	47·2
303-78	Folui	<i>Notopterus notopterus</i>	5·6	4·8	21·6	18·3
209-72	Magur	<i>Clarius batrachus</i>	11·3	9·8	48·7	44·2
1120-103	Rohu (jheel)	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	23·2	22	171·1	163·7
8650-168	Rohu	..	20·1	18·6	158·9	152·5
1480-415	Boal	<i>Wallago attu</i>	7·6	6·1	20·4	18·3
912-126	Mrigal	<i>Cirrhina mrigala</i>	14·8	12·6	32·3	29·2
150-45	Bam	...	3·2	3·1	11·3	9·8
6050-1530	Pangash	<i>Pangasius pangasius</i>	26·3	24·4	39·2	35·6
250-82	Bugda Chingri	...	6·5	6·3	54·1	47·4
11036-7320	Dhain	<i>Silonia Sillundia</i>	18·8	16·0	127·4	116·3
119-48	Royna	...	7·6	5·3	11·8	10·2

in the muscle, *viz.*, 30 mg. per cent. The next best muscle sources are *Pangash* (*Pangasius pangasius*) and *Rohu* (*Labeo rohita*). The concentration of the vitamin is highest in the *Rohu* fish liver, *viz.*, 171.1 mg. and then comes *Dhain* liver (*Silonia Silundia*), *viz.*, 127.4 mg. The difference between the total and free ascorbic acid is much greater in the case of liver than in muscle. It has also been found that both in the liver and muscle, the vitamin C concentration decreases as the size of the fish increases.

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